

E4.6.2: Final design of zero-touch and proactive network management

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4 List of Acronyms

6G	Sixth-Generation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCM	Life-cycle Management
LTN	Logic Tensor Network
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MR	Machine Reasoning
NeSy	Neuro-Symbolic
RAN	Radio Access Network
SoTA	State-of-The-Art
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
vRAN	Virtualised RAN
XAI	Explainable AI
ZSM	Zero-Touch Service Management

5 Executive Summary

Deliverable E4.6.2, titled "Final Design of Zero-Touch and Proactive Network Management," marks the completion of task A4.2 in the 6GENABLERS project (IA for 6G: Ultra Automation and Optimization, reference number TSI-063000-2021-10). Building on E4.3.2, this deliverable presents an enhanced approach for proactive, zero-touch management in future 6G networks. It leverages Neuro-Symbolic (NeSy) AI tools, particularly Logic Tensor Networks (LTN), to develop an efficient CPU resource prediction service that balances the trade-off between over-provisioning and under-provisioning through the use of smooth logical predicates in the model's loss function. These predictions will inform the intelligent orchestrator for anticipatory scaling actions during the integration phase. The designed algorithm is highly adaptable to both online and offline telemetry data metrics, aligning with ETSI ZSM's closed control loop framework.

The report begins with an exploration of the rationale behind CPU prediction and its critical connection to network performance, followed by an introduction to NeSy's concept and its transparency. It then outlines the model architecture and describes the O-RAN experimental dataset used. The deliverable delves into the NeSy formulation, presenting key results that show NeSy's superior performance over the state-of-the-art DeepCog model by minimizing both under- and over-provisioning. Additionally, a complexity analysis is conducted, comparing NeSy to baseline models. The report concludes with a discussion on adherence to the ETSI ZSM closed-loop framework, as well as the integration of OPTARE's telemetry system and OpenNebula orchestrator.

6 Introduction

In the rapidly approaching era of 6G networks, defined by extraordinary connectivity requirements and the rise of resource-intensive applications like holoportation, proactive management through predictive models becomes a crucial necessity. As technology advances, the need for sophisticated predictive analytics grows, with real-time responsiveness and seamless performance being essential.

A key focus of proactive management in 6G networks is the accurate prediction of CPU utilization. Recent experimental studies have highlighted the critical importance of CPU prediction, demonstrating its impact not only on application performance but also on key network components like virtualized Radio Access Network (vRAN) functionality, as discussed in the initial section of this report.

Thus, employing predictive models to forecast CPU demands is vital for enabling proactive scaling decisions. In this context, the combination of OPTARE's telemetry system, i2CAT's analysis/NeSy predictive model, MLOps pipelines, and OpenNebula's intelligent orchestrator creates a zero-touch closed control loop.

7 NeSy AI-Based Proactive Prediction Service

This section presents 6GENABLERS-AI techniques for proactive zero-touch management through *Neuro-Symbolic (NeSy)*-empowered CPU prediction service. Later, during integration phase, this service will allow the orchestrator to make anticipatory scaling decisions.

7.1 Motivation

In future-proof 6G virtualized networks, the allocation of CPU resources is closely related to the network performance¹. For instance, experimental evaluations² have demonstrated a non-linear relationship between bitrate, virtual RAN (vRAN) bandwidth, and CPU utilization. Even with sufficient radio resources, network performance suffers without adequate computational resources in the O-Cloud. Thus, strategic and coordinated CPU allocation is imperative for effective 6G network management. Artificial intelligence and machine learning play pivotal roles in optimizing CPU resources to bolster network performance across different technological domains. However, transparency and interpretability of these models is crucial to facilitate informed resource allocation decisions, where striking a delicate balance between over-provisioning and under-provisioning is essential for optimal *proactive resource prediction*, that adapts to network dynamics, and achieve cost-effectiveness³. In this respect, *DeepCog*, a solution for cognitive resource management in 5G networks was introduced⁴, aiming to bridge the trade-off between resource overprovisioning and service request violations. Moreover, resource allocation in virtualized RAN networks was evaluated within the O-RAN framework⁵, highlighting the detrimental effects of misallocation on performance. Given the distributed nature of O-RAN, federated reinforcement learning emerges as a promising approach to enhance predictive models while safeguarding privacy⁶. However, these studies often lack clarity regarding the interpretability of their predictive models, a prevalent challenge in AI/ML adoption within the telecommunications sector. Given the limitations of neural networks in terms of interpretability and systematic generalization, there is a growing acknowledgment of the significance of machine reasoning (MR) – a *Neuro-Symbolic* AI approach⁷. Addressing these

¹ M. Polese, L. Bonati, S. D'oro, S. Basagni, and T. Melodia, "Understanding o-ran: Architecture, interfaces, algorithms, security, and research challenges," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 25, pp. 1376–1411, 2022.

² María Hervás-Gutiérrez, Eduardo Baena, Carlos Baena, et al. Impact of CPU Resource on vRAN Performance in O-Cloud. TechRxiv. July 30, 2023.

³ M. Kalntis, G. Iosifidis, and F. A. Kuipers, "Adaptive resource allocation for virtualized base stations in o-ran with online learning," 2023. Allocation

⁴ D. Bega, M. Gramaglia, M. Fiore, A. Banchs, and X. Costa-Perez, "Deepcog: Cognitive network management in sliced 5g networks with deep learning," in *IEEE Conference on Computer Communications*, 2019, pp. 280–288.

⁵ C. Baena, M. Hervás-Gutiérrez, E. Baena, J. Villegas, R. Barco and S. Fortes, "Assessing the Impact of Computational Resources to the Quality of Experience Provided by vRANs," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 102944–102948, 2023, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3314853

⁶ H. Zhang, H. Zhou, and M. Erol-Kantarci, "Federated deep reinforcement learning for resource allocation in o-ran slicing," *IEEE Global Communications Conference*, pp. 958–963, 2022.

⁷ N. Duan, D. Tang, and M. Zhou, "Machine reasoning: Technology, dilemma and future," in *Proceedings of the Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing: Tutorial Abstracts*, 2020, pp. 1–6.

limitations, MR is viewed as an advanced solution to tackle both prediction tasks as well as ensure transparency through the embedded fuzzy logic⁸, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Neuro-Symbolic (NeSy) AI

7.2 NeSy Concept and Transparency

NeSy learning systems represent a fusion of symbolic and neural methodologies, leveraging the structured data proficiency of symbolic systems and the ability of neural systems to learn from unstructured data. This amalgamation presents a unified approach to problem-solving, offering higher-level reasoning outputs while learning from various data types⁹. In the context of learning for reasoning, this methodology integrates symbolic knowledge into the training process, utilizing neural systems for machine learning tasks. By incorporating symbolic knowledge, typically encoded for neural networks, this approach enhances interpretability and performance in complex tasks by guiding or constraining the learning process. A significant contribution in this domain is the introduction of Logical Tensor Networks (LTN)¹⁰. LTN represents a neuro-symbolic approach, serving as a framework that seamlessly integrates neural and symbolic methodologies for learning, reasoning, and querying both concrete data and abstract knowledge. Utilizing neural computational graphs and first-order fuzzy logic semantics, LTN presents a tensor-based formalism and introduces Real Logic, a fully differentiable logical language. It incorporates logical constructs such as predicates and axioms to enhance reasoning and interpretability in machine learning systems. Predicates capture relationships or properties, while axioms express general facts through logical assertions, enabling LTN to handle complex relationships, facts, and rules about entities within a domain. Consequently, it facilitates the development of AI models capable of anticipating and providing explanations for their predictions. Transparency is particularly crucial in telecommunications for understanding the decision-making processes of AI systems, especially within architectures like the 6G RAN Edge Cloud continuum. Integrating LTN into the proposed federated deep learning architecture not only enhances interpretability but also aligns with human cognitive processes, which is essential in dynamic telecom environments.

⁸ M. Orlić, M. Daoutis, and S. Singh, “An introduction to machine reasoning in networks,” Ericsson Blog, 2019.

⁹ D. Yu, B. Yang, D. Liu, H. Wang, and S. Pan, “A survey on neural-symbolic learning systems,” 2023.

¹⁰ S. Badreddine, A. d’Avila Garcez, L. Serafini, and M. Spranger, “Logic tensor networks,” *Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 303, p. 103649, Feb. 2022.

7.3 Architecture and Datasets

7.3.1 Architecture

Learning occurs iteratively through a runtime rule-based neuro-symbolic reasoning scheme in a closed-loop manner, as illustrated in Figure 2. Our model incorporates Logical Tensor Networks (LTN), which can perform both neural network-style learning and classical neuro-symbolic reasoning. In each local epoch, the Learner module feeds the posterior symbolic model graph to the Tester block, producing the test features and their corresponding predictions sent to the Knowledge Base Mapper at step 3. This integration is

Figure 2 NeSy-based proactive prediction design.

essential for implementing specific functions or services and contributes to the broader transition towards a more open, interpretable, and flexible 6G environment. During training, LTNs evaluate the satisfaction level of logical constraints based on the information from the Knowledge Base at step 4. The satisfaction level, denoted as ϕ , is transformed into a loss function during training using the formulation $loss = 1 - \phi$. Throughout the training process, optimization algorithms like the *Adadelta* optimizer operate to minimize this loss at step 5. These algorithms adjust the model's parameters, including weights and biases, to optimize satisfaction of logical constraints and minimize loss simultaneously. The goal is to identify optimal parameter values that strike a balance between accurate predictions and adherence to the logical rules encoded in the "eq" predicate, which we elaborate on in the following subsection.

7.3.2 Validation Dataset

The experimental dataset, as outlined in Table 1, corresponds to research detailed in¹¹, which focuses on instantiating varying numbers of vBSs on a shared computing platform. These vBSs are instantiated within specific CPU core sets, each with distinct time-sharing allocations. Each vBS is linked to a context that encompasses traffic demands and statistics on the used Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) for both Uplink (UL) and Downlink (DL). Notably, network parameters such as the MCS index significantly impact CPU load, particularly due to coding/decoding workloads. Furthermore, this dataset is structured as a time-series dataset, where each row represents a 20-second experiment under specific contextual conditions. It includes per-core CPU utilization, calculated as the average of samples collected every 200 milliseconds, providing a temporal dimension for analysing CPU utilization patterns over time. Note that although the dataset features might change in the integration phase, the NeSy model is generic and can be trained in different contexts.

¹¹ J. X. Salvat Lozano, J. A. Ayala-Romero, L. Zanzi, A. Garcia-Saavedra, and X. Costa-Perez, "O-ran experimental evaluation datasets," 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://dx.doi.org/10.21227/64s5-q431>

Table 1 Experimental O-RAN dataset

Feature	Description
mcs_dl_i	Downlink MCS index of vBS i
mcs_ul_i	Uplink MCS index of vBS i
dl_kbps_i	Downlink traffic demand in kbps of vBS i
ul_kbps_i	Uplink traffic demand in kbps of vBS i
cpu_set	Computing set used by vBS i
Output	Description
cpu_i	Avg. measured CPU utilization between 0 and 1.

7.4 Formulation

Figure 3 Knowledge Base Components

Knowledge Base Mapper: Within the Logical Tensor Networks (LTN) framework, the knowledge base assumes a pivotal role as it serves as a central repository for storing and organizing information in a formalized manner. In LTN, the knowledge base typically comprises predicates, axioms, and various logical constructs designed to encapsulate relationships, facts, and rules pertinent to entities within a specific domain. This knowledge base establishes the foundation for logical reasoning and decision-making within the framework, facilitating the representation and manipulation of intricate knowledge structures.

Language Preliminaries:

LTN utilizes a many-valued first-order logic (FOL) language denoted by L . This language includes a set of domains (D), constants (C), variables (X), function symbols (F), and predicate symbols (P). Logical formulas in L encode background knowledge relevant to specific tasks. A knowledge base (KB) is defined as $KB = \{D, X, C, F, P\}$. The syntax of LTN follows FOL, using predicate symbols and logical connectives like negation (\neg), conjunction (\wedge), disjunction (\vee), implication (\rightarrow), and quantifiers (\forall, \exists).

Grounding:

Grounding (G) is a critical process in LTNs that maps abstract logical constructs from the knowledge base to real-world data by mapping first-order logic elements onto numerical data through neural computational graphs. Grounding provides interpretation for domain symbols and non-logical symbols in L. For example, the grounding of vBS (virtual Base Stations) involves mapping its characteristics onto real-time performance data, and similarly, grounding CPU utilization connects CPU metrics to operational constraints in O-RAN architecture.

Grounding Functions:

- $G(x)$: Grounding function for variable x , maps input data to a feature matrix $X \in R^{m \times L}$, where m is the number of samples.
- $G(y)$: Grounding function for variable y , maps CPU utilization data to a vector $Y \in R^{m \times 1}$, where m is the number of samples.

Grounding of Functions:

The function $G(f^*(x)|\theta)$ represents the output of a multilayer perceptron (MLP) architecture defined as: $G(f^*(x)|\theta) = \text{MLP}_\theta(x)$

Where $\text{MLP}_\theta(x)$ consists of 2 hidden layers with 11 neurons each, an activation function σ , and a linear output layer with a single neuron.

Predicates: Predicates within the knowledge base delineate relationships or properties among entities. Our predicates are defined, drawing inspiration from a recent work¹², which introduced a "smooth" variant of the equality symbol "=" through a predicate termed "*eq*." The *eq* predicate is outlined as:

$$eq(f(x), y) = \frac{1}{1 + \alpha \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (f(x_i) - y_i)^2}}$$

In this context, the expression $eq(f(x), y)$ represents the result of the "*eq*" predicate applied to the predicted value $f(x)$ and the observed value y . The parameter α is a positive constant that governs the degree of smoothness in the matching process. This formulation guarantees outputs within the $[0, 1]$ range, with higher values indicating closer matches between the predicted and observed values. In our O-Cloud scenario, the "*eq*" predicate imparts essential domain-specific knowledge by facilitating flexible matching between predicted $f(x)$ and observed y CPU usage in a continuous and smooth manner. This adaptability is crucial for enhancing vRAN network performance in O-RAN deployment, as conventional strict equality constraints can prove excessively rigid, posing challenges for optimization efforts.

Axioms: Axioms comprise logical statements or rules that articulate fundamental truths within the knowledge base, directing the inference process based on the relationships defined by predicates. The logical connections stipulated by predicates within axioms empower the system to deduce new insights. During training, Logical Tensor Networks (LTNs) assess the satisfaction level of logical constraints derived from the information in the knowledge base, as depicted in step 4. This satisfaction level quantifies the extent to which the model conforms to specified logical rules, such as the "*eq*" predicate, during predictions. A high satisfaction level (approaching

¹² C. Fiandrino, L. Bonati, S. D'Oro, M. Polese, T. Melodia, and J. Widmer, "Explora: Ai/ml explainability for the open ran," Proc. ACM Netw., vol. 1, no. CoNEXT3, nov 2023.

1) corresponds to minimal loss (nearing 0), indicative of adherence to logical constraints. Conversely, a low satisfaction level (near 0) results in significant loss (close to 1). The goal of training is to minimize this loss, which essentially maximizes the satisfaction level of the logical axiom. The axiom is given by:

$$\mathbf{A}(y_k^{(i)}, \hat{y}_k^{(i)}) = \mathbf{Forall}(\mathit{ltn.diag}(y_k^{(i)}, \hat{y}_k^{(i)}), \mathit{eq}(y_k^{(i)}, \hat{y}_k^{(i)}))$$

This equation encapsulates a logical statement incorporating quantifiers specifically, universal quantification denoted by *Forall*, a diagonal operator *diag*, an equality predicate *eq*, and the regressor function $f(x_i) = \hat{y}_k^{(i)}$. In essence, it asserts that for all pairs of variables the equality predicate should hold between truth $y_k^{(i)}$ and prediction $\hat{y}_k^{(i)}$. The *Forall* quantifier indicates that this condition must, due to the *diag* operator, hold true for every pair of $(y_k^{(i)}, \hat{y}_k^{(i)})$. Furthermore, in a regression task, it is imperative to define a notion of equality. Hence, we introduce the predicate *eq* as a smoothed version of the symbol "=", transforming the constraint $y_k^{(i)} = \hat{y}_k^{(i)}$ a smooth optimization problem. The procedural steps are delineated in Algorithm 1.

Table 2 NeSy Algorithm

Algorithm 1: FLMR Approach

```

Input:  $K, \eta_\lambda, T, L$ . # See Table II
Server initializes  $\mathbf{W}^{(0)}$  and broadcasts it to the CLs
# Federated Learning
for  $t = 0, \dots, T - 1$  do
  parallel for  $k = 1, \dots, K$  do # Model graph from the
    local Model
    Receive the graph  $\mathcal{M}_k$  from the local model
    # Test the local model and send
    corresponding results to the Knowledge Base
    Mapper.
    # Use "eq" predicate to measure the
    satisfaction level  $\phi$ 
     $\mathit{eq}(f(x_i), y_i) = \frac{1}{1 + \alpha \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^N (f(x_i)_j - (y_i)_j)^2}}$ 
    # Calculate the loss function
     $\ell(y_k^{(i)}, \hat{y}_k^{(i)}) = 1 - \phi(y_k^{(i)}, \hat{y}_k^{(i)})$ 
    # Then Adadelta optimizer - minimize this
    loss, which essentially maximizes the
    satisfaction level of the logical axioms.
     $\mathbf{A}(y_k^{(i)}, \hat{y}_k^{(i)}) = \mathbf{Forall}(\mathit{ltn.diag}(y_k^{(i)}, \hat{y}_k^{(i)}), \mathit{eq}(y_k^{(i)}, \hat{y}_k^{(i)}))$ 
    Each local vBS  $k$  sends  $\mathbf{W}_k^{(t)}$  to the aggregation server.
  end parallel for
  # FL Server Aggregation
  return  $\mathbf{W}^{(t+1)} = \sum_{k \in \{k_1, \dots, k_m\}} \frac{D_k}{D} \mathbf{W}_k^{(t)}$ 
  and broadcasts the value to all local vBSs.
end

```

Definition 1 (*Satisfaction Level*):

A continuous parameter known as the satisfaction level ϕ of logical constraints within LTNs signifies the degree to which the model aligns with predefined logical rules, such as the "eq" predicate, throughout the training process. This metric is computed based on data from the knowledge base at a specific stage. Typically, ϕ ranges from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating a more substantial adherence to the logical prerequisites.

7.5 Results

7.5.1 Convergence and Satisfiability

Figure 4a illustrates that NeSy achieves quicker convergence compared to the DeepCog baseline model. In Figure 4b, the satisfaction levels over epochs for both models are depicted, specifically focusing on the satisfaction level of the predicate eq. Notably, the NeSy model achieves a highly favourable satisfaction level consistently hovering around 1.0, indicating superior performance. In contrast, the baseline DeepCog demonstrates a comparatively lower satisfaction level. NeSy's superiority can be credited to its incorporation of logical reasoning through Logical Tensor Networks (LTNs), which adeptly manage logical constraints.

Figure 4 Convergence and Satisfiability

7.5.2 CPU Usage Evaluation

Figure 5 Comparative Analysis of CPU Usage Load Prediction

The proposed model's accuracy in forecasting CPU load usage is compared to that of the baseline model. As depicted in Figure 5a, the proposed model closely tracks actual CPU load, demonstrating its effectiveness. Conversely, as illustrated in Figure 5b, the baseline model

encounters challenges in making precise predictions, underscoring its limitations. The superior performance of the NeSy model can be attributed to its distinctive design features, such as federated learning for collaborative learning, neural-symbolic artificial intelligence for interpretability, and adaptive resource management for responsive handling of CPU demand fluctuations.

7.5.3 Over-provisioning and Under-provisioning Trade-off Analysis

Figure 6 Trade-off between the resource over-provisioning (Red level) and under-provisioning (Blue level)

Figure 6 illustrates the analysis of the trade-off between resource over-provisioning and under-provisioning in the proposed NeSy model compared to the baseline. The figure depicts prediction errors for 100 samples at the conclusion of the training period. The red segment signifies over-provisioning, where predicted resources surpass actual requirements, while the blue segment indicates under-provisioning, which poses a risk of Service Level Agreement (SLA) violations due to insufficiently allocated resources. As depicted in 6a, NeSy effectively balances this trade-off, minimizing both over-provisioning and under-provisioning. This performance outperforms the DeepCog baseline model depicted in 6b by a *factor of 6*, as DeepCog consistently exhibits overprovisioning.

Figure 7 Provisioning CDF

7.5.3 Execution Time and Computational Complexity Evaluation

We can observe the computational complexity to provide insights into operational performance of the model, enabling informed decisions in resource-constrained environments. We compute the total FLOPS (Floating-Point Operations Per Second), FT for both approaches using the library¹³ with the following formula:

$$F_T = m \times n_{rounds} \times n_{clients} \times (F_f + F_b)$$

where n_{rounds} is the number of rounds, $n_{clients}$ is the number of clients, m is the number of samples for each client, F_f and F_b are the FLOPS for the forward and backward passes of the model, respectively. Both approaches exhibit the same computational time complexity, resulting in 152.50 GFLOPS. However, the FLMR approach demonstrates a slightly faster execution time, despite having the same FLOPS count. This difference in execution speed can be attributed to more efficient resource management, such as reduced communication overhead or better parallelization in FLMR, making it more performant in practical scenarios while maintaining the same computational load.

Table 3 Complexity comparison

Metric	DeepCog	FLMR
Total Time (50 rounds)	61.5228 seconds	60.0746 seconds
FLOPS	152.250 GFLOPS	152.250 GFLOPS

¹³ M. Tokusumi, “keras-flops: Flops calculator for keras models.” [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/tokusumi/keras-flops>

8 Compliance with ETSI Closed Loop Automation

Figure 8 6GENABLERS-AI components to adhere to ETSI closed loop management

The architecture aligns with the principles and requirements outlined by the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) Zero-touch Network and Service Management (ZSM) framework in terms of:

- **Closed-Loop Automation:**
 - OPTARE's *Telemetry platform* exposes data in both offline (training) and online (inference) modes.
 - Transparent MLOps pipeline namespace leverages this telemetry data to train and refine *NeSy proactive CPU prediction model*. The predictions are then served to OpenNebula's decision engine co-located with the orchestrator, to perform scaling actions.
 - This closed-loop automation process ensures that the architecture can adapt to changing conditions and optimize resource utilization without manual intervention.

ETSI ZSM emphasizes closed-loop automation to achieve self-optimization, self-configuration, and self-healing capabilities, which this architecture demonstrates by dynamically scaling and optimizing Edge applications based on telemetry data and AI models.

- **End-to-End Service Management:**
 - The architecture covers the entire service lifecycle, from data ingestion and telemetry collection to machine learning model training and application scaling.
 - By integrating Edge and cloud resources, it enables end-to-end service management and optimization, ensuring efficient and reliable operation of Edge applications.

ETSI ZSM promotes end-to-end service management to achieve service agility, flexibility, and optimization, all of which are supported by this architecture through its seamless integration of Edge and cloud environments.

In summary, the architecture aligns with ETSI ZSM principles by enabling service orchestration, closed-loop automation, and end-to-end service management. It demonstrates how Edge computing can be integrated with cloud resources to achieve efficient, automated, and optimized service delivery in compliance with ETSI standards.

9 Conclusion

Deliverable E4.6.2 marks a key milestone in the 6GENABLERS-AI project's task A4.2, focused on driving ultra-automation and optimization in 6G networks. The innovative use of Neuro-Symbolic (NeSy) AI tools, particularly Logic Tensor Networks (LTN), is central to the proactive zero-touch management strategy. By creating an efficient CPU resource prediction service that carefully balances over-provisioning and under-provisioning, this deliverable paves the way for anticipatory scaling during integration tasks. A thorough analysis and comparison with the state-of-the-art DeepCog show the NeSy predictor's superior performance, highlighting its potential to optimize CPU allocation and boost overall network efficiency. This success not only deepens the understanding of how CPU prediction impacts network performance but also reflects the project's alignment with industry standards like ETSI ZSM, where OPTARE's monitoring, i2CAT's prediction service, and OpenNebula's scaling decision/actuation would form a closed control loop, adapting seamlessly to both online and offline telemetry data metrics.